

KNOWLEDGE OF HEALTH CONSEQUENCES OF RAPE AMONG FEMALE SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENUGU EAST LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: *The study sought to determine the knowledge of Health consequences of Rape among secondary school students in Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu State. Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. Three research questions and one null hypothesis were formulated to guide the study. The sample for the study was 399 secondary school students drawn from a population of 1393 students from 29 secondary schools in Enugu East Local Government Area using two-stage sampling procedures. Structured questionnaire titled “Knowledge of Health Consequences of Rape Questionnaire (KHCRQ)” was the instrument used for data collection. The instruments was validated by 3 experts from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education and 1 from Maths and Computer Departments. The reliability of the instrument yielded 0.82 reliability index indicating that the instrument was reliable. Frequencies and Percentages were the statistics used for data collection. The findings were; the students in Enugu East Local Government Area have high knowledge (60.4%) of physical health consequences, social health consequences and mental/emotional health consequences of rape*

Key words; *Knowledge, health consequences. Rape, secondary school students*

Introduction

Rape constitutes myriads of health problems especially among youth in developed and developing Nations like Nigeria. Rape is a traumatic experience that affects the victim (also known as survivor) in a physical, psychological and sociological way (Basil 2014). It is a type of sexual assault. It can be described as forced sexual intercourse without consent. It involves sexual penetration which could be vaginal, anal or oral. This penetration may be with a body part or an object. It is an act of physical, psychological and emotional violation in form of sexual act, inflicted on someone without their consent (kemi, 2020). The act may be carried out by physical force, coercion, abuse of authority or against a person who is incapable of giving valid consent, such as one who is unconscious, incapacitated, has an intellectual disability or is below the legal age of consent (WHO, 2012). Rape can be defined as unlawful sexual activity and usually sexual intercourse carried out forcibly or under

threat of injury against a person's will or with a person who is beneath a certain age or incapable of valid consent because of mental illness, mental deficiency, intoxication, unconsciousness or deception. World Health Organization and other agencies have also expanded rape beyond traditional definition. The WHO (2017) defines rape as sexual assault which is a form of sexual violence. It is an act in which a person purposefully touches another in a sexual way without the person's consent. It usually involves the use of coercion or physical force in which the victim engages in sexual act against their will (Gbemi, 2018). The Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2015) include rape as a form of sexual violence which is the general term used to describe any kind of unwanted sexual act or attempt directed towards an individual, irrespective of the relationship to the victim. It includes activities such as rape, child sexual abuse, sexual assault, sexual harassment, female genital mutilation and others.

A United Nations statistical report compiled from government sources showed that more than 250,000 cases of rape were recorded by police annually. The reported data covered 65 countries (UN, 2022). Universally, rape is a serious crime that affects millions of people around the globe. According to WHO, approximately 1 in 3 women will experience sexual violence throughout their life time, with 7% of those women having experienced rape or attempted rape? Rape is considered to be an act which is not peculiar to any nation race or gender. Poverty stricken societies are prone to insecurity of life and properties through youth involvements in drugs and rape. Incidence of rape varies in different parts of the world. British Broad Casting Cooperation [BBC, 2022] reported that between April to December 2022 there were about 50,000 rape offences recorded by police in England and Wales. Of these offences, about 900, amounting to fewer than 2% have so far resulted in a charge or court summons. Of the bulk of the cases, more than 20,000 have had to close because the victim has withdrawn from legal proceedings. While in United States of America, cases of rape are about 212,190 as reported by Department of Justice. The plaque of sexual violence at universities across the United States of America has become such a problem that it captured the attention of the White house. (Diana 2014)

In a survey by United Nations (2015), 23% of Italian women suffered violence in their lifetimes, 3.3% had experienced attempted rape and 2.3% had experienced rape. In Australia, the reported rape rate per 100,000 people is relatively high, although in decreasing trend, coming down from 91.6% reported rape in 2023 to 28.6% in 2010. In a study carried out in Botswana (UN, 2022) showed 4.6% women had been raped in their lifetime and 4.2% had experienced attempted rape in their lifetime. In Brazil, in 2021, over 88% of reported rape cases had women and girls as victims. That year, half of those cases were against children aged 13 years old. Overall, there were more than 66,000 reported cases in Brazil (Teresa, 2021).

In Africa the story is the same. In Ghana, a survey revealed that 87% of Ghananian women reported having been raped by a man in their lifetime and 5% of men reported having been raped by a wife or

girlfriend (WHO, 2017). Ethiopia is estimated to have one of the highest rate of violence against women in the world. A report by UN showed that women in Ethiopia are most likely to suffer from domestic violence at the hands of their partners and that nearly 60% of Ethiopian women were subjected to sexual abuse (BBC, News, 2013).

In Nigeria, the case of rape follows the same trend with that of other countries. In Nigeria,; finding from national survey carried out in 2014 on violence against Children confirmed one out of four females reported experiencing sexual violence in childhood with approximately 70% reporting more than one incident of sexual violence. In same/ study, it was found out that 24.8% of females ages 18 – 24 years experienced sexual abuse prior to age 18 of which 5.0% sought help with only 3.5% receiving any services (WARIF, 2022). According to Amnesty International, police forces in Nigeria are reported to have perpetrated acts of rape and other sexual abuse against women in public locations or while women were being transferred to police stations or while women visited their male detainees in police custody and sometimes police used sexual violence in order to extract confession and other information from the women (Olevia, 2020)

The true incidence of rape is not known in Nigeria. The current incidence may be an under estimation mainly due to fear and stigmatization which limits reportage. By 2010, despite the fact that rape is abhorred by Nigerian law, culture, religion and anecdotal evidence suggests that the incidence appears to be increasing. Enugu State, being an integral part of Nigeria, is not excluded from this public health challenge. Majority of the students in secondary schools have been victims of rape or attempted rape according to EU report 2014. Women and girls continue to be failed by a system that makes it increasingly difficult for survivors to get justice, while allowing perpetrators to get away with gross human right violations (Osai, 2021). S Rape has become prevalent in our society today and unfortunately a lot of survivors are afraid to speak up because of the stigma attached to it. Society would rather blame the survivors than blame the perpetrator who is supposed to take the sole responsibility of the decision made to violate another (Kemi 2020). The silence can take a roll on the survivor and negatively affect their mental health and overall wellbeing. This may linger for as long as nothing is done about it. It is in response to this challenge that Sexual Assault Referral Centres (SARCs) like women At Risk International Foundation (WARIF) centers are established to help survivor find their voices and offer them medical, psychological, shelter and legal support as they embark on their healing journey (WARIF, 2022). One victim, Vera Uwailo Omosuwa, a 22 year-old Microbiology student was raped and brutally assaulted in 2020 in a church near her home in Benin, Edo State and died a couple of days later from her injuries. Hamira, a five-year-old, was drugged and raped by her neighbor in April 2020. Her injuries were so bad that she could no longer control her bladder. Several other students like Barakat Bells, an 18-year-old student, were raped during robbery in her home in Ibadan, Oyo state. She was butchered with machet by her rapists and died on 1st June, 2020.

The covid-19 pandemic only exposed what has been going on for so long. Not only are women and girls being raped in Nigeria, but when they are brave enough to come forward their report to the police, they are being dismissed by police officers as liars and attention seekers (Osai, 2021). Worrisome aspect is that some people do not have the knowledge of the health consequences of this ugly action.

Rape was devastating consequences. These consequences are categorized into physical, social and mental consequence. Physical health consequences of rape are enormous. Rape accounts for 8.8% and 5.6% of gynecological emergencies in Enugu State, South East Nigeria (Ajah; 2018).

Injury and pregnancy can also result from rape because most penetrative rape generally does not involve the use of condom. Injury can potentially lead to serious outcome (Smother, 2011). Physical consequences can arise from both forced sexual assault and those not involving forcible admission such as drug assisted rape. Forced sexual assault frequently causes visible bruising, or bleeding in and around the vaginal or anal area and bruises on other parts of the body from coercive violence. (Ajah 2018). Other physical consequences of rape includes: virginities, nail marks, and shock because of the incidence; sexually transmitted infection and chronic pelvic pain can also occur because boys who do such practices are normally dirty and care free.

Surprising, many students have limited knowledge of physical consequences of rape. Ugwuoke (2022) found in his study that primary school children in Abia State have very limited knowledge of rape. Continuing. Ugwuoke claimed that this lack of knowledge promoted the wide spread rape in Abia State.

Socially, the consequences of rape is excruciating. In some places, girls who are raped are often forced by their family to marry their rapist because being a victim of rape and losing virginity carry extreme social stigma and the victims are deemed to have their reputation tarnished. Withdrawal from social activities and function coupled with the avoidance of rape victims are part of the social consequences of rape. According to Pauwels (2013), American criminologist, observed that emotional damage of child raped often leads to girls growing up into lives of prostitution, crime and desolation or even promiscuity. To them also low self- esteem could result, while at the other end of the condition in which a woman is incapable of enjoying sex occur (dyspareunia). Some people die during or after rape, others remain traumatized for life. Some contract sexually transmitted infections like HIV/AIDS, syphilis, gonorrhoea chlamydia etc while others may bleed to death. In many cases unwanted pregnancy can lead to crude abortions that may cause permanent damages to the individual reproductive system. Some pregnancy may remain and be carried to term with shame attached to it. (Naake; 2016). According to Campbell (2013) rape is a social problem that can lead to suicide or suicidal attempt. . Just like the knowledge of physical consequences of rape, Ugwuoke (2022) maintained that knowledge of social and mental health consequences among female secondary school students in Abia State is also low especially in rural area where more of the incidence are reported.

The mental consequences of rape is exceedingly intense. Victims experience both short and long term psychological consequences of rape like anxiety and depression. Psychological adverse consequences of rape include intense feeling of shame, guilt (Gluck,2018). These feelings are worsened by the lack of support from family, friends or authorities. It therefore becomes pertinent for the researcher to investigate knowledge of health consequences of rape among secondary school students in Enugu East local government area.

The choice of secondary school students was informed by the fact that these group of people were future of the nation. They are the future work force and have to develop physically, mentally and socially well in order to be able to match their future challenges that awaits them. Their being raped cause them physical, mental and social unwell which will result in unwanted pregnancy, diseases, abortion which will eventually cumulate into death or withdrawal from school. This withdrawal from school will make acquisition of talent and skills for proper future takeover of the nature's work force will not possible thereby affecting the nation's sustainable national development. This is worrisome and informed the need for this study.

To give direction to this study three specific purposes and research questions and one hypothesis were raised to guide the study.

Purpose of the Study

Generally, this study was set out to determine the knowledge of health consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East Local Government Area, Enugu State. Specifically, this study sought to determine the:

1. Level of knowledge of physical health consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A
2. Level of knowledge of social health consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A
3. Level of knowledge of mental health consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the level of knowledge of physical consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A
2. What is the level of knowledge of social consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A
3. What is the level of knowledge of mental consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A

Hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.5 level of significance.

1. This is no significant different in the level of knowledge of rape among female secondary school students based on location.

Methods

The descriptive survey research design was used for the study. This design was considered appropriate for the study because it involved a fraction of the population that has the same characteristics. According to Idoko (2012), a study is termed a survey if data are collected from or about just the same member of the population which represent the entire group. The population for this study was 13930 secondary school students from 29 public secondary schools in Enugu East L.G.A. The sample size for the study was 399 students which are determined by the use of Taro Yamene (1964) formular. The sample was arrived at by the use of two- stage sampling procedure. First stage involved the use of simple random sampling techniques where 6 schools were sampled from the 29 schools. Secondly, systematic sampling technique was used to sample 399 students from the 6 sampled schools. Structured questions titled “knowledge of Health Consequences of Rape Questionnaire (KHCRQ)” was the instrument used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Human Kinetics and Health Education and one from Science and Computer Department, all in Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT). Reliability of the instrument was established through the administration of the instrument on secondary school students from Enugu South Local Government Area who are not part of the main study. Kuder Richardson was used to calculate the co relation coefficient of the instrument which yielded .87 reliability index. The researcher and two-briefed research assistants administered the questionnaire and collected immediately they were completed. Out of 399 copies of questionnaire that were distributed, 341 copies (urban 220 and rural121) were properly filled, returned and were used for analysis. Data collected were tallied and analyzed and findings reported in frequency and percentages.

Results

Research question 1: What is the level of knowledge of physical health consequences of rape among secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage response score of Secondary School Students on the level of knowledge of physical health consequence of rape

S/N	Physical Consequences of Rape	True		False		Decision
		Freq	%	Freq	%	
1	Tearing of the vulva	286	83.9%	55	16.1%	High
2	Nail marks and searches on the body	126	36.1%	215	63.1%	Low
3	Emaciation due to the shock of the incident	288	84.5%	53	15.5%	High
4	STI/HIV infection	242	71.0%	99	29.0%	High
5	Death may occur	218	63.9%	123	36.1%	High
6	Perforation of the rectum	78	22.9%	263	77.1%	Low
	Average		60.4%		39.6	High

The data presented in Table 1 showed that out of the 6 items for determining knowledge of Physical health consequences of rape among secondary school students only items 2 (item 2, 6) have the values below 40%. The remaining 5 items (item 1, 3, 4, 5) have their values above 60%

In overall or generally, the data in table 1 indicated that the students (60.4) have high knowledge of consequences of physical health consequences of rape.

Research question 2: What is the level of knowledge of social health consequences of rape among the Secondary School Students in Enugu East L.G.A?

Table 2: Score of Secondary School Students on the level of Knowledge of Social Health Consequences of a and Percentage Response Rape.

S/N	Social health Consequences	True		False		Decision
		Freq	%	Freq	%	
7	Isolation from friends	280	82.1%	61	17.9%	High
8	Disappointment and hatred	78	22.9%	263	77.1%	Low
9	School drop out	268	78.6%	73	21.4%	High
10	Missing of school due to injury	277	81.2%	64	18.8%	High
11	Suicidal Behaviour	126	36.1%	215	63.1%	low
12	Shame	302	88.6%	39	11.4%	High
13	Loss of self esteem and worth	110	32.3%	231	67.7%	Low
Average			60.3%		39.7	High

The data presented in table 2 showed that out of the 7 items for determining knowledge of social health consequences of rape among secondary school students only 3 items (item 8, 11 and 13 items) have value below 40%. The remaining 4 items (item 7, 9, 10 and 12) have values above 60% (High).

In overall or generally, the data in the table indicated that the students have high (60.3) knowledge of social health consequences of rape.

Research Question 3: What is the level of knowledge of mental/emotional health consequences of rape among secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A.?

Table 3: Frequency and Percentage Response Score of Secondary School Students on the Level of Knowledge of Mental/Emotional Health Consequences of Rape.

S/nn	Mental/emotional health consequences of rape	True		False		Decision
		Freq	%	Freq	%	
14	Self withdrawal	273	80.1	68	19.9	High
15	Depression	281	82.4	60	17.5	High
16	Aggression	126	36.8	215	63.9	Low
17	Suicidal ideation	115	33.7	226	66.3	Low
18	Inferiority complex	288	84.5	53	15.5	High
19	Deviant behavior	110	32.3	231	67.7	Low
20	May not be in touch with reality	260	76.2	81	23.8	High
Average percentage			60.8		39.2	High

The data presented in table 3 showed that out of the 7 items for determining knowledge of mental/emotional health consequences of rape among secondary school students only 3 items (16, 17 and 19) have values below 40%. The remaining 4 items (item 14, 15, 18 and 20) have values above

60%. In overall or generally, the data in table 3 indicated that the students have high (60.8%) knowledge of mental/emotional health consequences of rap Hypothesis.

There is no significant difference in the level of knowledge of health consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Enugu East LGA based on location

Table 4: Summary of Chi-square Statistics on the Level of Knowledge of Health Consequences of Rape between Urban and Rural Female Secondary School Students in Enugu East LGA

Location	Frequency of Respondents		Total	Df	P value	Decision
	Correct	Incorrect				
Urban	126	94	220	339	.000	Reject (Significant)
Rural	83	38	121			
Total	209	132	341			

The table above shows that the p-value (.000) is less than 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that the null hypothesis is rejected or that it is not significant.

Discussion

The finding pertaining to research questions¹ revealed that the knowledge of physical health consequences of rape among the secondary school students in Enugu East L.G.A was high. The findings is expected because health education is studied in secondary schools where students ought to be taught about rape and its consequences. It is also a welcome development because the high knowledge of rape will save the students from embarrassing consequences of rape like abortion and unwanted pregnancy However, the finding is in contrast with Ugwoke (2022) who found low level of knowledge of rape among secondary school female student in Abia State.

The finding pertaining to research question 2 and 3 indicated that female secondary school students have high level of knowledge of social and mental/emotional health consequences of rape. This finding is in disagreement with the finding of Ugwuoke(2022) who maintained that knowledge of social and mental health consequences of rape among female secondary school students in Abia State is low. This differences maybe as a result of distance

The finding pertaining to hypothesis is that there is a significant difference between urban and rural female secondary school students in Enugu East LGA in the level of knowledge of health consequences of rape. This shows that the knowledge of health consequences of rape among female secondary school students is depended on location. This finding is in agreement with that of Ugwuoke (2022) who maintained that there is low level of knowledge of social and mental

consequences of rape among female secondary school students especially in rural areas where more of the incidence are reported.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study it was concluded that the knowledge of health consequences of rape among female secondary school students was high and that the knowledge was dependent on location.

Recommendation

Based on the findings, therefore the following recommendations were made:

1. The Post School Management Board(PPSMB) Enugu State should be organizing seminars and workshops on rape to enable student get more knowledge on rape and its consequences. Also, in the seminars and workshops the ways of avoiding rape should be taught.
2. Individuals should be encouraged to report any case of rape to the appropriate quarters.

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